

ENTREPRENEURIAL VARIANCES AMONG GENDERS: A STUDY OF UTTARAKHAND

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Abstract

When all revenue in an economy is used effectively, economic progress can be said to be effective. One of the important resources that must be used effectively for the prosperous growth of any economy is human capital. One way to analyse the consumption of human capital is to look at everyone's equal participation in the economy. Numerous categories are classified by age, income, gender, ethnicity, caste, and other factors inside the economy. Every set of people that make up each subgroup must participate equally. The growth of the economy is negatively impacted by inequality in any of the groups. One of the guiding principles for enhancing the use of human capital might be the establishment of fair and equal opportunities for all individuals, irrespective of their group membership. The current study focuses on how women's contributions compare to men's on equal footing.

Keywords: Gender equality, Entrepreneurship, Motivational factors, Entrepreneurial issues

Introduction

In comparison to a few decades ago, the global economic position now presents a different image. Over the past few decades, the global economy has changed. In terms of trade volume, industrial sector, technology, and industrial and service sector diversification, the strength of diverse economies has increased. In the current age of globalization, privatization, and liberalization, every economy strives for growth and development in order to raise the living standards of its citizens. "Gender Equality and Development" highlights the importance of gender equality in terms of raising production, enhancing the representation of institutions, and improving the development results for the next generation. One way to break the cycle of poverty is to promote women's and rural entrepreneurship while reducing gender inequalities. To achieve the resilient economic growth that would lift people out of poverty, it is

essential to mobilize the potential production of rural residents, especially women. Gender equality has been seen as one of the key tactics to lower poverty and increase work chances since women are thought to play a vital role in society and the health of the family and community. Not only do men and women participate in income-producing activities insufficiently, but there is also cause for concern regarding the prominence of employment opportunities. In addition to unequal female engagement in the economy, the presence of vulnerable employment and a greater need in the agricultural sector are equally responsible for the decline in efficiency and the issues that follow. Over time, the structure of many economies has changed in relation to work. A crucial position has been held by the services sector in many different economies. Nonetheless, in many economies, especially emerging economies, agriculture remains the primary source of income. The difference in the per capita income of men and women in the economy is caused by the inadequate involvement of women in activities that generate revenue. Gender inequality is a result of income disparities in human progress. Gender disparity has a detrimental impact on the growth and development of an economy since it reduces its competitiveness. Consequently, investigating new avenues for producing revenue is just as vital as focusing on the increased involvement of women in economic activity. Gender disparity in income and, consequently, in human development within the Indian economy can be attributed to women's unequal participation in economic activities. To effectively utilize an economy's fruitful potential, alternative income-generating opportunities must be built, and labour force from agriculture must be rapidly redirected to the industrial and service sectors.

Review of Literature

Numerous research on gender equality and men's and women's entrepreneurship have been carried out worldwide. These studies have attempted to examine the motivational elements that drive both male and female entrepreneurship as well as the challenges that each gender faces while starting or running their own businesses. Several research that are now available on the pertinent literature are listed below:

Kumar and Kalyani (2011) analysed the association between motivational and entrepreneurial factors to suggest the educators for improved entrepreneurial education and training involvements. The data set consists of 144 out of 432 companies, representing the sample size. Using SPSS, data has been analyzed using

regression testing, correlation analysis, and descriptive statistics. According to the study, entrepreneurial and motivational factors are significantly correlated with each other, and entrepreneurial factors are significantly impacted by motivational elements. A skilled individual can obtain financial plans for their business. Women have considerably safer times when it comes to paying back debt. Low self-confidence and low motivation are caused by inadequate training and education for female entrepreneurs, which also affects issues with funding, profit positioning, sales support, and self-assurance.

Kumari and Mor (2021) identified issues and difficulties that Rajasthani rural women entrepreneurs in the Jhunjhunu district faced. Thirty women entrepreneurs and thirty non-entrepreneurs made up the sample size, and information was gathered through interviews. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive figures. The study's conclusions demonstrate that women in both groups experienced discrimination based on factors such as gender, caste, and educational attainment. Obstacles for female businesses include sales and raw material availability. Women who are not entrepreneurs confront prejudice, a lack of help in building a network, and interference from family members. Another problem they encounter is a lack of knowledge about government initiatives like tax breaks, concessions, subsidies, and financial and technical support for starting their own businesses, obtaining raw materials, and arranging financing.

Ward et al. (2019) identified actionable ideas for economic growth and gender equality. Gender equality has been shown to support economic growth with the help of specific evidences. The current analysis puts pressure on encouraging data, such as the fact that gender equality leads to a spike in human capital stock, more viable labour and product markets, and better physical capital investment. The efficiency of agriculture decreases as a result of gender disparity. It has also been explained how gender equality affects the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals.

Dollar and Gatti (1999) examined the question of whether growth, income inequality, and gender inequality are favourable to women. The current study took the position that economic advancement and gender parity go hand in hand. It has been argued that underinvesting in women's education is a bad economic decision. According to the study, gender differences are beneficial for slower growth. It has been determined that

investing in female education boosts national income. Increased funding has been carefully considered to promote greater gender equality in education and other fields. By shedding light on the perception and circumstances of entrepreneurship in the pre-colonial and colonial era, the first half of the twentieth century, following the world wars, in Independent India, and in the present,

Mathew (2017) identified SMEs and its new perspectives on HDI and the origin of entrepreneurship in India. The businesses established in India to foster entrepreneurship have been given labels. It has been explained how the growth of entrepreneurship has affected the globalization age. Additionally, the status of entrepreneurship, the inventiveness displayed, and its significance for SSIs is evaluated in relation to countries such as Europe, India, the US, the Philippines, and South Africa. Also discussed are the updated views on entrepreneurship and what has to be done.

Bekele and Worku (2008) looked at the variables that affect an enterprise's long-term viability and practicality. The study's goals were to pinpoint the primary predictors of survival and determine if businesses run by men outperform those run by women in terms of performance. Of the 500 businesses included in the study, 221 (or 44%) were run or owned by women. 112 variables were covered by the structured questionnaires used to gather the data. Data analysis was done using STATA version 10 of the Statistical Package. Research indicates that of all the businesses that failed, 78% were run or controlled by women. Of all the inefficient businesses run by or owned by women, 69% of them required work to obtain a loan from reputable lenders, 66% were unable to reinvest a portion of their profits, 72% lacked managerial expertise, 74% lamented their lack of procedural knowledge, and 55% had only a low level of education.

Objectives of the study

- To present entrepreneurial issues faced by men and women entrepreneurs.
- To present motivational factors of men and women towards entrepreneurship.

Methodology

The descriptive research design was adopted for this study that established the effects of implementation of motivational factors towards entrepreneurship development and issues or challenges faced by men and women in Uttarakhand state. This design facilitated the researcher to use quantitative research methods in collection

of data, analysis, and interpretation. This research required a convenience sampling method used to draw sampling units. A sample of 100 entrepreneurs were conveniently chosen from the area of both manufacturing and service sectors for this research. The collection of data was done through both primary and secondary sources. Select men and women entrepreneurs were the main source of primary data collection. Sources of secondary data obtained for the research were various journals, books, websites, government publications, and reports published by govt. departments etc. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics.

Data Analysis

Issues faced by the men and women entrepreneurs

Various entrepreneurial problems related to the accessibility of capital, raw material, marketing, support from government, family & spouse, dealing with dual responsibilities of work as well as household, etc. have been analysed and discussed in the study.

Table 1: Issues faced by the men and women entrepreneurs in Uttarakhand

Issues faced by entrepreneurs		Not a problem	Minor problem	Moderate problem	Major problem
Support from spouse	For men	43	4	1	2
	For women	45	3	1	1
Support from family	For men	36	7	4	3
	For women	43	2	2	3
Dual responsibilities of managing household chores along with enterprise	For men	33	8	6	3
	For women	38	7	3	2
Gender discrimination while selling products/ services in market.	For men	36	11	2	1
	For women	41	7	1	1
Gender discrimination in availing finance/access to capital	For men	27	8	6	9
	For women	30	9	4	7
	For men	33	6	7	4

Gender discrimination in availing needs of raw material	For women	34	8	4	4
Gender discrimination in training and support from government	For men	32	7	0	11
	For women	32	7	1	10

Source: Researcher’s Compilation

According to the information in Table No. 1, marital support-related concerns were not a concern for the majority of male and female entrepreneurs (43% and 45%, respectively). 43% of women and 36% of men who were entrepreneurs said that they had no trouble getting family support. 38% of women and 33% of men who were entrepreneurs said it was easy to balance their business and domestic duties. Gender discrimination was not a concern for 41% of women and 36% of men who were entrepreneurs offering goods or services in the marketplace. For 27% of men and 30% of women who were entrepreneurs, there was no issue with gender discrimination when it came to obtaining financing or capital. Gender discrimination was not an issue for 33% of men and 34% of women who were entrepreneurs, according to raw material needs assessments.

Motivational factors of men and women towards entrepreneurship

This section discusses the degree of encouragement of all the motivating aspects in starting a business for both men and women entrepreneurs. The table below shows the percentages of both groups of entrepreneurs who had varying levels of stimulus from each factor. The following table shows the correlation between the variables that encourage someone to pursue entrepreneurship and their level of success:

Table 2: Motivational factors of men and women towards entrepreneurship

Motivational factors	Men entrepreneurs	Women entrepreneurs
Self confidence	50	30
Economic necessity	44	40
Wish to improve quality of life	47	40
Social recognition	30	25
Previous occupation	27	20
Market competitiveness	25	20

Inspiration from success of others	44	50
Government policies & programs	25	20

Source: Researcher's Compilation

As per the above table no. 2, self- confidence was a motivating factor for 50% of men and 30% of women entrepreneurs. Economic necessity was a motivating factor for 44% of men and 40% of women entrepreneurs. Wish to improve quality of life was a motivating factor for 47% of men and 40% of women entrepreneurs. For 30% men and 25% of women entrepreneurs, social recognition was a motivating factor. Previous occupation of entrepreneurs of 27% of men and 20% of women entrepreneurs was a motivating factor. Market competitiveness factor was a motivation for 25% of men and 20% of women entrepreneurs. Inspiration from success of others was a motivating factor for 44% of men and 50% of women entrepreneurs. And lastly, govt.policies & programs were motivating factor for 25% of men and 20% of women entrepreneurs.

Conclusion

Multiple factors contribute to the growth of entrepreneurship. The socio-economic profile of an entrepreneur, enterprise traits, entrepreneurial skills, government backing, motivating factors for pursuing entrepreneurship, and challenges encountered by entrepreneurs all have an impact on the degree of success experienced by an entrepreneur. Therefore, a thorough analysis of all the variables and an exploration of the roles that each one plays is essential to the further development of entrepreneurship. The challenges and motivating elements that both male and female entrepreneurs must overcome are crucial to their business's success. The study's conclusions can serve as the foundation for the growth and development of entrepreneurship among both men and women. Analysis of the impact of various factors on entrepreneurs' accomplishment levels has diverted attention from problems and trouble spots that need to be addressed for entrepreneurship to flourish.

Based on the opinions shared by the male and female entrepreneurs, the following sources can be deduced:

- It is necessary to upgrade basic infrastructure, such as the water supply, roads,

and electricity.

- Financial incentive schemes for exporters ought to be implemented.
- More buyer-seller events ought to be planned.
- Schemes should be used to assist new and small exporters.
- Suitable procurement of raw resources.
- It is necessary to increase program applicability, awareness, and transparency.
- Assistance with registration and other legal requirements ought to be given.
- There should be a relaxation of the requirements and processes for registering an enterprise.
- The government should continue to run training programs to foster entrepreneurship.
- Promote entrepreneurship among younger people.

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